

1 **Structural similarity between the minimal component of the bacterial cell wall, peptidoglycan**
2 **(MDP) and amino acids suggests bacterial, pattern-associated feedback at mTOR and amino acid**
3 **sensors of the secretory pathway.**

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10 Citations

11 1. Roychowdhury, A., Wolfert, M.A. and Boons, G.J., 2005. Synthesis and proinflammatory
12 properties of muramyl tripeptides containing lysine and diaminopimelic acid moieties. *ChemBioChem*,
6(11), pp.2088-2097.

13 2. Kubasch, N. and Schmidt, R.R., 2002. Synthesis of muramyl peptides containing
14 meso-diaminopimelic acid. *European Journal of Organic Chemistry*, 2002(16), pp.2710-2726.

15 3. Cottagnoud, P., Gerber, C.M., Majcherczyk, P.A., Acosta, F., Cottagnoud, M., Neftel, K., Moreillon,
16 P. and Tauber, M.G., 2003. The stereochemistry of the amino acid side chain influences the inflammatory
17 potential of muramyl dipeptide in experimental meningitis. *Infection and immunity*, 71(6), pp.3663-3666.

18 4. Parant, M., 1979, May. Biologic properties of a new synthetic adjuvant, muramyl dipeptide (MDP).
19 In *Springer Seminars in Immunopathology* (Vol. 2, No. 1, pp. 101-118). New York: Springer-Verlag.

20 5. Audibert, F., Chedid, L., Lefrancier, P., Choay, J. and Lederer, E., 1977, April. Relationship
21 between chemical structure and adjuvant activity of some synthetic analogues of
22 N-acetyl-muramyl-L-alanyl-D-isoglutamine (MDP). In *Annales D'immunologie* (Vol. 128, No. 3, pp.
23 653-661).

24 6. Audibert, F., Parant, M., Damais, C., Lefrancier, P., Derrien, M., Choay, J. and Chedid, L., 1980.
25 Dissociation of immunostimulant activities of muramyl dipeptide (MDP) by linking amino-acids or peptides
26 to the glutaminyl residue. *Biochemical and Biophysical Research Communications*, 96(2), pp.915-923.
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